

Polypyridyl ruthenium complexes binding with nucleic acids

Liang-Nian Ji^{a*} and Jin-Gang Liu^{a,b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Zhongshan University, Guangzhou, 510275, P. R. China

E-mail : cesjln@zsu.edu.cn Fax : 0086-20-84035497

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Tongji University, Shanghai, 200092, P. R. China

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The binding mechanism and interactions between the octahedral polypyridyl ruthenium(II) complexes and DNA are reviewed. The influence of ligands including the intercalative ligand and the ancillary ligands on DNA-binding behavior, enantioselectivity, the nonradioactive nucleic acids probes and DNA molecular light switches are discussed, respectively. Focus on the modification of the ligands resulting in the photophysical properties of metal complexes and the DNA-binding properties emphasized.

Introduction

Nucleic acids under physiological conditions are polyanions composed of heterocyclic based linked to sugar phosphate backbone which adopt a variety of conformations. The regular DNA secondary structure are well characterized, and the B-DNA is regarded as the most common structure, with a right-handed helix, ten base-pairs per turn, quasi-perpendicular to the main axis. The wide major groove and narrow minor groove are both well solvated by water molecules. A-DNA which is also a right-handed helix, has 11 residues per turn, with tilting of the bases of 20°. This helix is fairly stiff, with a deep and narrow major groove and a broad and shallow minor groove. While Z-DNA is a left-handed helix which is long and slender. The major groove is in fact a shallow, almost convex surface, and the minor groove is a narrow crevice, zigzagging in a left-handed fashion along the side of the major groove. These different DNA forms play important biological roles, but there is an important need in methods and tools in order to determine local topologies or structures of DNA and relate them with the function of nucleic acids. Therefore it would be particularly attractive to have a battery of molecular tools so as to detect, *in vitro* and or *in vivo*, the appearance of one of the systems.

Transition metal complexes are possible molecular tools for the study of nucleic acids. Stable, inert to substitution, rigid and structure well-defined complexes containing spectroscopically active metal centers are extremely valuable as probes of biological systems. The design and construction of small transition metal complexes with polypyridyl ligands for use as DNA structure probes or artificial nuclease have been an active area of research during the last 20 years or so¹⁻⁸. However, the design possibility has remained largely

unexploited in studies of small metal complexes with DNA. The binding mechanism, especially the factors which govern groove position, are still not fully understood. In this paper we do not provide an exhaustive review of the literature, but instead to serve as a report that highlights the binding mechanism of polypyridyl ruthenium complexes with nucleic acids, and the complexes to be served as luminescent reporters for DNA instead of using radioactive markers.

Background of metal complexes as DNA structure probes

The first experiments describing the interactions of coordinatively saturated octahedral transition metal complexes with DNA involved the use of tris(phenanthroline) complexes of zinc, cobalt and ruthenium⁹⁻¹⁶. From the earliest studies it has been demonstrated that chiral metal complexes show some enantiospecificity in their interactions with DNA. Based on the photophysical and equilibrium dialysis studies of [Ru(phen)₃]²⁺, Barton and coworkers¹² proposed that the Δ enantiomer, a right-handed propeller-like structure, would display a greater affinity than the Λ enantiomer for the right-handed DNA helix owing to the different steric constraints imposed on the isomers, and it was that difference that determined the enantiomeric selectivity. In the most extreme case of [Ru(DIP)₃]²⁺ (DIP = 4,7-diphenyl-1,10-phenanthroline), it was reported that Λ -[Ru(DIP)₃]²⁺ can not interact with B-DNA at all, while Δ -[Ru(DIP)₃]²⁺ binds at least as strongly as [Ru(phen)₃]²⁺. Since Λ -[Ru(DIP)₃]²⁺ appeared to bind to Z-DNA, it has been suggested as a probe for non-B-form DNA¹¹. Later, Λ -[Ru(TMP)₃]²⁺ (TMP = 3,4,7,8-quadamethyl-1,10-phenanthroline) has been shown to bind selectively to A-form polynucleotides¹⁴, suggested as chiral probe for A-form helices. Chiral discrimination of

this type seemingly depends on matching the symmetry of the metal complex with that of the double helix. Studies with these simple complexes provided a basis for conceptualizing how octahedral complexes might interact noncovalently with DNA and for exploring how the properties of metal complexes, e.g. their photophysical characteristics, might be utilized in developing novel probes for DNA.

Binding mechanism of polypyridyl ruthenium complexes with DNA

[Ru(phen)₃]²⁺ binding with DNA :

It has been shown that polypyridyl ruthenium(II) complexes can bind to DNA noncovalently in a number of ways, such as external electrostatic, groove binding and intercalation. As mentioned above, the matching of the shape of the complexes and the local DNA-binding sites has an impressive effect on the binding mode.

Although numerous studies have appeared, the exact binding mechanism of the prototype of $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ with nucleic acids remains a vigorous debate. Using electric dichroism, Yamagishi¹⁷ was able to show that the C₃ axis of the optically active forms of Δ - and Λ - $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ were oriented differently relative to the DNA helix axis in the ruthenium-DNA complex. It was concluded¹⁸ that Δ enantiomer bound to DNA with one of its phenanthroline ligands intercalated between the base pairs while Λ enantiomer was not intercalated but was instead bound by an electrostatic mechanism.

In an extensive investigation involving unwinding studies using closed circular DNA and absorption and fluorescence spectroscopies, Barton and coworkers¹⁰ stated that both the Δ and Λ enantiomer intercalated between the base pairs of DNA. Both isomers unwound ColEI DNA, leading to the conclusion that intercalation was an important binding mode. This conclusion was further proved by the studies of binding of Δ - and Λ - $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ to nucleic acids of different base composition and structure using equilibrium dialysis and photophysical methods¹². Using an assay involving the DNA unwinding enzyme topoisomerase I, Kelly and coworkers¹⁹ showed that racemic $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ unwound covalently closed circular pBR 322 DNA, thus confirming the earlier Barton's unwinding studies, and it was suggested that the coordination compound bound to DNA by intercalation. The possibility that the ruthenium complex could only partially insert one phenanthroline ring was then suggested by Barton¹⁰, Kelly¹⁹ and Gorner²⁰, respectively. In a later work using NMR measurements, Rehmann and Barton^{15,16} concluded that Δ enantiomer prefers intercalation while Λ enantiomer prefers surface binding to $[\text{d}(\text{GTGCAC})_2]$ and $[\text{d}(\text{CGCGCG})_2]$.

Hiort and coworkers²¹ provided another view of the ruthenium-DNA interaction. Based on the linear dichroism measurements, it was concluded that each isomer bound to DNA by a single binding mode and that neither isomer bound to DNA by intercalation. This conclusion was further supported by two-dimensional NMR measurements²² which showed that both Δ and Λ enantiomer bound by a nonintercalative mode within the major groove of DNA.

Satyanarayana and coworkers^{23,24} used viscosity, competition dialysis experiments as well as spectroscopic methods to investigate the interaction of $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ with DNA, and they argued that both isomers bound to DNA by a single mode and neither Δ nor Λ isomer bound to DNA by classical intercalation. The interactions were entropically driven. Neither isomer exhibited significant selectivity for B- and Z-DNA.

Most recently, Rodger and coworkers²⁵ studied the interactions of calf thymus DNA, poly(dA-dT)₂ and poly(dG-dC)₂ with the two enantiomers of $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ by normal absorption, linear dichroism, circular dichroism and computer modeling. From the results, it was concluded that the binding mode depended on the metal complex concentration. For the Λ isomer the partially inserted mode is favored at all mixing ratios. For the Δ isomer at low-R (isolated metal complex binding) minor groove binding is preferred. However, at high R (close packed metal complexes) the slotted mode became more favorable and some major groove partial insertion also occurred. Magically, at low-R this suggested binding mode contrasts completely with Bartons binding model.

[Ru(phen)₂DPPZ]²⁺ binding with DNA :

Unlike the prototype $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$, there is a consensus about classical intercalative binding of the dipyrrophenazine ruthenium complexes, $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{DPPZ}]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{DPPZ}]^{2+}$, with DNA²⁶⁻³³, which has been unambiguously confirmed by NMR^{28,29}, resonance Raman^{30,31}, and linear dichroism spectra³², as well as viscosity measurements³³. These two complexes show no photoluminescence in aqueous solution at ambient temperature but luminesce brightly upon binding to DNA, displaying the characteristic of molecular light switches. The binding reaction was proposed to be driven primarily by hydrophobic interactions, hydration changes, and polyelectrolyte effects resulting from the release of condensed counterions. The luminescence restored was proposed to be the protection of the phenazine nitrogen atoms from solvent water when the DPPZ ligand intercalated between the base pairs of DNA. Based on the two-dimensional ¹H NMR experiments, Dupureur and Barton^{28,29} proposed that Δ -

$[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{DPPZ}]^{2+}$ intercalated into the base pairs of the oligonucleotide $\text{d}(\text{GTCGAC})_2$ from the major groove side of the B-form duplex.

Recently, photophysical studies of Δ - and Λ - $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{DPPZ}]^{2+}$ bound to calf thymus DNA, T4 DNA, and several synthetic DNA polymers were carried out³⁴. On the basis of the difference in emission characteristics among these DNAs, it was concluded that $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{DPPZ}]^{2+}$ isomers bound by intercalation from the minor groove of the DNA helix. Barton and coworkers³⁵ reinvestigated the binding of Δ - $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{DPPZ}]^{2+}$ to poly(dA), poly(dG), and calf thymus DNA by time-resolved luminescence spectroscopy and described experiments in which well-characterized major and minor groove DNA binding agents competed with $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{DPPZ}]^{2+}$ for DNA binding sites. The experimental results demonstrated and also supported the original assignment of ruthenium complex intercalation from the major groove side of duplex DNA.

$[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{dpq}]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmphen})_2\text{dpq}]^{2+}$ binding with DNA :

Removal of the terminal aromatic ring on the DPPZ ligand yields dipyrido[2,2-*d* : 2',3'-*f*]quinoxaline (dpq), a closely related analog to DPPZ. ¹H NMR experiments recently^{36,37} indicated that Δ - $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{dpq}]^{2+}$ bound to a hexanucleotide $\text{d}(\text{GTCGAC})_2$ by intercalation from the minor groove. Interestingly, the chemical shift perturbation and nuclear Overhauser effects observed with intercalation of this compound differ significantly from those described for $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{DPPZ}]^{2+}$.

On addition of methyl groups at the 2 and 9 positions on the phenanthroline rings, Collins and coworkers³⁸ used ¹H NMR spectroscopy and viscosity measurements to study the oligonucleotide binding of the Δ - and Λ - $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmphen})_2\text{dpq}]^{2+}$ (dmphen = 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline). The addition of either enantiomer to $\text{d}(\text{GTCGAC})_2$ induced large upfield shifts and significant broadening for the hexanucleotide imino and metal complex dpq resonances. These data together with the intermolecular NOE results strongly suggested that both of the isomers intercalated from the minor groove. The results also implied that the dpq ligand of the Δ enantiomer intercalated deeply into the hexanucleotide base pairs while the Λ enantiomer can only partially intercalate.

Intercalation from the minor groove by these octahedral metal compounds was unexpected, given the steric bulk of the nonintercalating phenanthroline ligands and the narrowness of the DNA minor groove. It is remarkable how apparently minor changes in the ligand architecture and electronic structure can lead to profound influence on binding geometries. Obviously it is not simply a steric consideration that

governs the groove position of the intercalation. Then, what determines the groove access of the octahedral compound?

$[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HPIP}]^{2+}$ binding with DNA :

Very recently, the interaction of the isomers of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HPIP}]^{2+}$, containing an extended planar area of phenanthroline ligand HPIP (HPIP = 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)imidazo[4,5-*f*][1,10]phenanthroline), with a hexanucleotide $\text{d}(\text{GTCGAC})_2$ was studied by NMR spectroscopy³⁹. Addition of the isomers to the oligonucleotide induced significant upfield shifts for the HPIP resonances, while much less smaller perturbations were observed for the ancillary bpy ligands. Upon binding with the isomers, the sugar protons of C3H2'-H2'' and G4H2'-H2'' which locate in the major groove of the oligonucleotide showed the largest chemical changes. Intermolecular NOE cross-peaks between the HPIP and the hexanucleotide major groove protons were also observed. These results as well as the photophysical and viscosity studies suggested that both of the enantiomers of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HPIP}]^{2+}$ bound DNA by intercalation from the major groove.

Influence of ligands on DNA-binding behavior :

The design of metal complexes which act like sequence-specific proteins, recognizing the structure texture of the DNA as well as the electrostatic potential and H-bonding patterns in the groove is our utmost objective. However, a better understanding of which features are required of a complex to result in a desired mode of binding is absolutely needed at first. As have shown in literature, modification of the ligands may result in not only the changing of chemical, photophysical, and photochemical properties of metal complexes, but also the DNA-binding properties.

Influence of the intercalative ligand : Among the discussion of DNA-binding modes of Ru^{II} complexes, the intercalation mode has attracted more attention since the established applications are almost related to this binding mode^{4,40-43}. The DNA-binding behaviors of the series of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{L}]^{2+}$ (L = IP, PIP, CIP, MCP, NIP, NOP, HPIP, HNAIP, HNOIP, CNOIP) have been observed by photophysical methods and viscosity measurements⁴⁴⁻⁵⁹. For $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{IP}]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{PIP}]^{2+}$, their DNA-binding behavior indicated that both of them bound with DNA by intercalation, however, the latter was suggested to be more strongly intercalated to the DNA than the former⁴⁸. It was reasoned that the nearly coplanar PIP ligand possesses a larger planar area and a more extended π system than that of IP, and therefore PIP would penetrate more deeply into, and stack more strongly with the base pairs of DNA. An *ortho*-phenolic group that may form an intramolecular hydrogen bond with the nitrogen atom of the imidazole ring was in-

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of the ligands mentioned in this review

produced to extend the planarity, formed as ligand HPIP. Going from $[Ru(bpy)_2HPIP]^{2+}$, $[Ru(bpy)_2PIP]^{2+}$ to $[Ru(bpy)_2HNAIP]^{2+}$, the intrinsic binding constants follow $6.5 \pm 0.3 \times 10^5$, $4.7 \pm 0.2 \times 10^5$ and $8.3 \pm 0.4 \times 10^4 M^{-1}$, respectively⁵⁴. This result suggested that the introduc-

tion of a phenolic group into the HPIP molecule may have some additional affinity to stabilize the binding of the complex to DNA. Although the larger coplanar area of the HNAIP ligand is expected, $[Ru(bpy)_2HNAIP]^{2+}$ has the lowest affinity to CT-DNA among the three compounds. It

seemed that the large naphthyl ring may lie out of the plane of the imidazole ring, resulting in the partial intercalation of the HNAIP ligand.

In $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{CIP}]^{2+}$, owing to the steric interaction between the chloro substitute and the imidazole ring, the 2-chlorophenyl group is remarkably twisted with respect to the IP plane forming a dihedral angle of 44.5° . It was concluded⁵² that the torsion between the aromatic rings of CIP, due to the introduction of the bulky substitute, resulted in $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{CIP}]^{2+}$ only partially intercalating into DNA, and subsequently reduced the DNA-binding affinity.

It is very interesting to compare the photophysical properties of the complexes $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HPIP}]^{2+}$, $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HNOIP}]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{CNOIP}]^{2+}$ binding with DNA⁵⁶. $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HPIP}]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{CNOIP}]^{2+}$ can emit luminescence in Tris-buffer at ambient temperature, but no luminescence was observed for $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HNOIP}]^{2+}$. Upon addition of calf thymus DNA, their luminescence behaviors were distinctly different. $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HPIP}]^{2+}$ exhibited an obvious emission enhancement ($I/I_0 = 2.7$) when DNA was added. For $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HNOIP}]^{2+}$, the suppressed emission can be revived by the addition of double strand DNA, showing the characteristics of DNA molecular light switch. On the other hand, with increasing amounts of calf thymus DNA, the emission intensity of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{CNOIP}]^{2+}$ decreased dramatically (Fig. 2). The DNA-binding result suggested that the introduction of a nitro group to the HNOIP ligand is responsible for the absence of luminescence of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HNOIP}]^{2+}$ in water. By addition of double strand DNA, $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{HNOIP}]^{2+}$ may intercalate its HNOIP ligand into the base pairs of DNA, shielding the ligand esp. the nitro group from solvent water and restoring its luminescence. Given the excited state's oxidation potential of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{CNOIP}]^{2+}$ ($E^{*2+/+} = 0.89$ vs SCE) is lower than that of the most easily oxidized guanine base ($E_{\text{G,G}^+}^* \sim 1.0$ vs SCE), $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{CNOIP}]^{2+}$ emission quenching by calf thymus DNA was suggested to proceed via a non-electron transfer mechanism. Compared with those emission quenching by B-DNA, which proceeds via an electron transfer mechanism involving guanine base oxidation^{66–68}, this quenching behavior is quite rare. The crystal structure of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{CNOIP}]^{2+}$ showed⁷¹ that for the CNOIP ligand the 2-chloro-5-nitrophenyl group twists dramatically to the IP plane with a dihedral angle of 58.7° , which resulted in a partial intercalation of the CNOIP ligand into the base pairs when the compound bound to calf thymus DNA. From this remarkable difference of the DNA-binding photophysical properties, it clearly demonstrated how the ligand design can be used to tune its DNA-binding properties.

Fig. 2. Emission spectra of (A) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{HNOIP})]^{2+}$ and (B) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{CNOIP})]^{2+}$ in the absence and presence of increasing amounts of calf thymus DNA $[\text{Ru}] = 20 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DNA}] = 0 - 1.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The binding behavior of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{AFPNP}]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{AFPNP}]^{2+}$ to calf thymus DNA has been reported^{60,61}. For AFPNP, the nitrogen atom of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ is sp^2 hybridized, which makes the phenyl ring incline to one-side of the ligand. As a result, $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{AFPNP}]^{2+}$ bound to the double helix mainly by external electrostatic interaction. While for $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{AFPNP}]^{2+}$, the remote phenyl in AFNP can rotate to become coplanar with flourenamine moiety, then it can bind with DNA by intercalation. These results demonstrated that modification of the ligand may lead to substantial changes in the binding modes and affinities of the complexes to DNA.

DNA-binding properties of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{tatp})]^{2+}$, $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dptatp})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dmtatp})]^{2+}$ were investigated to see how the intercalative ligand's steric hindrance influenced their association with DNA⁶³. Morgan and co-

workers⁶⁹ discussed the effects of ligand planarity on intercalative binding of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{L}]^{2+}$ ($\text{L} = \text{PPZ}, \text{dpp}, \text{qpy}$) to calf thymus DNA.

Effects of the ancillary ligands : The ancillary ligands were also to play an important role in governing DNA-binding of the complexes. However, it has received less attention in comparison with the intercalated ligand. Given intercalation into the helix by one ligand, we can compare how different ancillary ligands add to or detract from the overall binding affinity.

The DNA-binding behaviors of complexes of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{atatp})]^{2+}$ (1), $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2(\text{atatp})]^{2+}$ (2) and $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmp})_2(\text{atatp})]^{2+}$ (3) ($\text{bpy} = 2,2'$ -bipyridine, $\text{phen} = 1,10$ -phenanthroline, $\text{dmp} = 2,9$ -dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline) revealed that changing the ancillary ligand from bpy to dmp not only decreased their binding affinity but also dramatically affected the binding mode of their association with DNA⁶⁵. Complexes 1 and 2 bind with calf thymus DNA in an intercalative mode but complex 3 in a non-intercalative one.

$[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ have been found to exhibit a molecular 'light switch' effect by intercalative binding to DNA. However, the information on the influence of the ancillary ligands on the optical properties of these complexes is modest. Nair and coworkers⁷⁰ reported a ruthenium complex of dppz , $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$, and found the complex showing no luminescence either in the absence or presence of DNA. It bound 40-fold lower to DNA than $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$. Recently, the complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{IP})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ ($\text{IP} = \text{imidazo}[4,5-f][1,10]$ phenanthroline) was reported⁵⁵ to display some different DNA-binding properties compared with the parent complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$. In contrast to $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$, the excited state profile of $[\text{Ru}(\text{IP})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ was associated with mono-exponential decays in the presence of DNA. The MLCT transition of $[\text{Ru}(\text{IP})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ was more sensitive to the presence of DNA than that of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$, and also the intrinsic binding constant was found to be several times larger than that of the parent complex. It was reasoned that the planar area of the ancillary ligand IP was larger than that of the bipyridine, certainly yielding a greater aromatic surface and increased hydrophobicity, which increased the overall affinity to DNA and consequently reduced the number of binding modes.

Going from $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmb})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ ($\text{dmb} = 4,4'$ -dimethylbipyridine) to $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmp})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ ($\text{dmp} = 2,9$ -dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline), their DNA-binding selectivity changed remarkably⁷¹. After 48 h dialysis against CT-DNA, the dialysate of $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmb})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ displayed two strong

CD signals with a positive peak around 275 nm and a negative peak around 295 nm; however, there appeared no CD signal for $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmp})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ in the similar conditions (Fig. 3). The crystal structure of $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmp})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ revealed that the dihedral angle between the plane of dppz and the plane of one of the dmp is only 50.8° ; while for $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmb})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$, the dihedral angle between the plane of dppz and dmb is almost 90° . It is the complex structure differences that distinguished their binding behavior with DNA.

Fig. 3. CD spectra of the dialysates of (a) $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmb})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$, (b) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ and (c) $[\text{Ru}(\text{dmp})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ after 48 h dialysis against CT-DNA; $[\text{Ru}] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DNA}] = 1.0 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$.

Enantioselectivity :

Tris-chelates of ruthenium(II) complexes with diimine ligands exist as a pair of enantiomers, and binding to chiral double-stranded polynucleotide constitutes a diastereomeric interaction which favors one isomer. The degree to which one isomer is favored has been documented and, in general, the Δ isomer appears to be favored in binding to right-handed helices. On the other hand, increasing exceptions to this have emerged in recent years.

For the complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$, no significant enantioselectivity was observed for binding to calf thymus DNA²⁷. Both enantiomers showed an intercalative binding via the dppz ligand significantly high binding constant. For B-form polynucleotides, the enantiomers of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{phi})]^{2+}$ showed a significant binding preference (ratio >1.5) for the Δ isomer in two cases and $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2(\text{phi})]^{2+}$ showed a significant preference for the Δ isomer with calf thymus DNA and for the Δ isomer in one case⁷². For the complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{dpphen})_3]^{2+}$ ($\text{dpphen} = 4,7$ -diphenyl-1,10-phenanthroline) it has previously been claimed^{11,73,74} that the Δ enantiomer interacted specifically with B-form DNA and the Λ enantiomer specifically with Z-form DNA.

However, recent results demonstrated that Δ - and Λ -[Ru(dpphen)₃]²⁺ bound non-intercalatively to B-form DNA and showed insignificant enantioselectivity in their interaction⁷⁵. For the extreme case of [Ru(bpy)₂(ppz)]²⁺ (ppz = 4,7-phenanthroline[6,5-*b*]pyrazine), which had been erroneously assumed^{69,76,77} that the Δ isomer bound more strongly to calf thymus DNA, approximately four-fold of the Λ configuration over the Δ configuration was favored in binding to CT-DNA⁷⁸. This phenomenon was attributed to the difference in interaction which was non-electrostatic in nature. Clearly, the configuration of the two ancillary ligands is not sufficient to predict which enantiomer will bind more strongly. More subtle interactions with the double strand B-form DNA structure, involving not only the ancillary ligands but also the partially intercalated diimine ligand, are involved.

There was no significant enantioselectivity in the interactions of complex of Δ - and Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂(HPIP)]²⁺ with double strand B-DNA. Both of the enantiomers showed the intercalative binding mode. However, different binding rates of the individual enantiomers were observed⁵⁶. The Λ enantiomer bound more rapidly than the Δ enantiomer, and their different penetration into the pairs of DNA upon binding to the double helix was suggested to be responsible.

Nucleic acids molecular light switches

Polypyridyl ruthenium complexes can provide sensitive luminescent probes for double strand DNA in solution, Nevertheless, two drawbacks at least prevent their broader application as general non-radioactive nucleic acid probes : the background luminescence of the free compounds in aqueous solution and their relatively weak binding to DNA. Complexes [Ru(bpy)₂(dppz)]²⁺ and [Ru(phen)₂(dppz)]²⁺, the most intensively investigated true molecular light switches for DNA, exhibit a negligible background emission in water but luminesce brightly in the presence of double strand of DNA with high binding affinity ($K_a \sim 10^6 M^{-1}$). The luminescence quantum yield was found to decrease from triplex DNA to Z form, to B form and finally to A form, reflecting the level of protection of the ruthenium luminophore from water quenching⁷⁹. An oligonucleotide containing the above ruthenium complex tethered to its terminus was prepared⁸⁰. Little luminescence was apparent for the single-strand complex, however, addition of the complementary strand yielded intense luminescence. In contrast, addition of a noncomplementary strand produced no detectable emission, and the emission intensity decreased with the base mismatches. The oligonucleotide-tethered complex therefore can function as a sequence specific molecular light switch.

[Ru(phen)₂(PHEHAT)]²⁺ was found to be a light switch as well⁸¹, although it displayed a weaker luminescence when bound to CT-DNA than did [Ru(phen)₂(dppz)]²⁺. [Ru(phen)₂(dicnq)]²⁺ was also claimed to be a molecular light switch for DNA⁸². The emission enhancement was quite impressive ($I/I_0 \sim 16$) in comparison with the enhancement observed for [Ru(phen)₃]²⁺, but it was relatively less pronounced compared to the strong molecular light switch effect for [Ru(phen)₂(dppz)]²⁺.

Recently, [Ru(bpy)₂(HNOIP)]²⁺ was reported to be DNA molecular light switch⁵⁷, which bound to DNA avidly ($K_a = 6.2 \times 10^5 M^{-1}$) via HNOIP intercalation between the base pairs of DNA. In aqueous solution the suppressed emission can be revived by the presence of double helical nucleic acids, such as calf thymus DNA, poly[dA-dT]₂ and poly[dG-dC]₂, with their emission maximum shifting from 607 nm for GC sequence to 615 nm for AT sequence (Fig. 4). Noticeably, the emission efficiency of [Ru(bpy)₂(HNOIP)]²⁺

Fig. 4. Emission spectra of [Ru(bpy)₂(HNOIP)]²⁺ ($10 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$) in 5 mmol dm^{-3} Tris-HCl, 50 mmol dm^{-3} NaCl buffer (pH 7.0) at 298 K in the presence of ($100 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$) (a) Poly[dA]•Poly[dT], (b) calf thymus DNA, (c) Poly[dG]•Poly[dC] and (d) absence of DNA.

in the presence of DNA was almost double that of the well known DNA molecular light switch [Ru(bpy)₂(dppz)]²⁺. The luminescence retrieval of [Ru(bpy)₂(HNOIP)]²⁺ in the presence of double strand DNA may be understood by comparing the structure of itself with [Ru(bpy)₂(HPIP)]²⁺ which showed intense luminescence in aqueous solution. The introduction of a nitro group to the HNOIP ligand was suggested to be responsible for the absence of its luminescence in water. Upon addition of double strand DNA, [Ru(bpy)₂(HNOIP)]²⁺ may intercalate its ligand HNOIP into the base

pairs of DNA, shielding the ligand esp. the nitro-group from solvent water and switching on its luminescence.

The luminescence of $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2(\text{tapt})]^{2+}$ can be restored by the addition of CT-DNA and the emission intensity enhanced with the increasing amounts of DNA (Fig. 5)⁶⁵. When the binding ratio $[\text{DNA}]/[\text{Ru}]$ varied from 5 : 1 to 40 : 1, the excited lifetime increased from 1717 to 2018 ns. The luminescence switch on effect by the presence of DNA was proposed to be the result of protection of the ligand dptatp, upon intercalating into the base pairs of DNA, from attacking by solvent water. $[\text{Ru}(\text{pztp})_2(\text{bpy})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{pztp})_2(\text{phen})]^{2+}$ showed negligible emission in water but emit luminescence in the presence of DNA, displaying the characteristics of molecular light switch for DNA⁸³. The

Fig. 5. Emission spectra of $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2(\text{tapt})]^{2+}$ ($2 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$) in the absence and presence of increasing amounts of calf thymus DNA; $[\text{DNA}] = 0 \sim 160 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$.

interactions of these two complexes with DNA were proposed to involve the base pairs intercalation of the bound ligand pztp. A similar mechanism to the light switch effect observed for $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ was also suggested for these compounds.

Flipping the molecular light switch off was achieved⁸⁴ by the formation of DNA-bound heterobimetallic complexes using $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{tpphz})]^{2+}$ and Cu^{2+} . In the presence of DNA, the intensity of the luminescence of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{tpphz})]^{2+}$ decreased as a function of Cu^{2+} , and the total loss of luminescence occurred at a ca. 1 : 1 $[[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{tpphz})]^{2+}]/[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ ratio. It was proposed that Cu^{2+} coordinated to tpphz from the opposite side of DNA helical axis with respect to the intercalated $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{tpphz})]^{2+}$, analogous to a molecular nut (the Cu^{2+} ion) and bolt (the $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{tpphz})]^{2+}$ complex) through DNA. The quenching mechanism was suggested to be the result of formation of a nonluminescence species, most likely the hetetobime-

tallic dimer $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{tpphz})\text{Cu}]^{4+}$.

Concluding remarks

The information about the interactions of the octahedral ruthenium complexes with DNA has improved enormously in recent years, although the factors which govern groove position for the access of the compound and enantioselectivity still remain unclear. By appropriate design of the ligands it is possible to change photophysical and photochemical properties dramatically, and to facilitate specific interactions between the metal complex and functional groups on the nucleobase, and eventually to achieve practical applications as DNA probes, or as 'artificial nuclease' or DNA-targeted phototherapeutic procedures. Studies with bifunctional compounds or oligonucleotides modified with transition metal complex will be both to increase the binding affinity of the compounds and to enhance the site specific targeting. More significant progress in use of these compound as tools of DNA probes will be expected in the next few years.

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